

THE EFFECT OF VILLAGE FUND ALLOCATION AND TRANSPARENCY ON THE WELFARE OF THE PANDE GAMPONG COMMUNITY, TANAH PASIR DISTRICT, NORTH ACEH REGENCY

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the effect of village fund allocation on the welfare of the Pande Village community, Tanah Pasir District, North Aceh Regency. This study uses a quantitative approach with primary data through a questionnaire to 100 respondents from a total population of 1,144 people. The results of the t-test indicate that the allocation of village funds has a partial significant effect on community welfare. Transparency has a partial significant effect on the welfare of the Pande Village community. In addition, the allocation of village funds and transparency together have a significant effect on community welfare. Therefore, the village government is advised to prioritize the use of village funds for economic empowerment programs, improving basic infrastructure, and the quality of education and public health.

Keywords: Village Fund Allocation, Transparency, Community Welfare

INTRODUCTION

The village is the smallest government unit that interacts directly with the community and therefore plays a strategic role in implementing central and regional government policies. The success of these policies depends heavily on the village's ability to exercise its authority. According to Sutoro Eko Yunanto (2015), a village is a legal community unit that has territorial boundaries, authority, and ancestral rights to regulate government affairs, community interests, and village development. The implementation of Village Fund Allocation (ADD) is regulated in various laws and regulations, including Law Number 32 of 2004, Government Regulation Number 72 of 2005, Regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs Number 37 of 2007, and is reinforced by circulars and village regulations. Law Number 6 of 2014 concerning Villages emphasizes that villages have the authority to manage government and development independently in order to realize advanced, independent, and democratic villages.

Village Fund Allocation (ADD) is one of the village's main sources of income, used to finance governance, development, and community empowerment. These funds are sourced from the Regional Budget (APBD) and transferred to the village treasury account. In Pande Village, village fund allocation plays a crucial role in supporting development in various sectors and improving community welfare. Therefore, transparency and community participation are key to managing Village Fund Allocation (ADD) to ensure sustainable and equitable village development. Pande Village has a population of 1,144, with the majority in the lower-middle income category. This indicates that the majority of the community is low-income, which impacts the needs and allocation of village funds. In 2022, the village fund allocation of Rp837,854,480 was used for various areas of governance, development, community empowerment, and disaster management.

However, conflict arose in its management due to a lack of transparency and community participation in decision-making. Village financial information was not widely disseminated, and village deliberations only involved a small portion of the community. Yet, transparency is a key principle of good

THE EFFECT OF VILLAGE FUND ALLOCATION AND TRANSPARENCY ON THE WELFARE OF THE PANDE GAMPONG COMMUNITY, TANAH PASIR DISTRICT, NORTH ACEH REGENCY

Khairunnisak et al

village financial governance. Previous research has shown that village fund allocation has a positive impact on community welfare, although social disparities persist due to income differences and unequal policies. To reduce the welfare gap, the village government implemented a Direct Cash Assistance (BLT) program for low-income communities. This program is considered to help alleviate the economic burden on the community, but requires proper management, evaluation, and oversight to ensure its targeted and sustainable distribution. Based on this, this study was conducted to examine the impact of village fund allocation and transparency on the welfare of the Pande Village community.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Village Fund Allocation (ADD) is part of the balancing funds received by districts/cities for village management. Each village receives a minimum village fund allocation of 10% of the central and regional financial balancing funds (Yuesti, 2023). These funds are used to finance governance, development, and community empowerment. Previous research has shown that village fund allocation has a positive impact on community welfare, contributing to infrastructure development, economic empowerment, and strengthening the education and health sectors in villages (Fathony & Aditya Achmad, 2019; Hariyani, 2018).

Transparency, on the other hand, refers to openness in managing information that is accessible to the wider public. Dwiyanto (2014) stated that transparency is crucial for increasing government accountability, particularly in village budget management. This openness allows communities to actively participate in program planning and evaluation, which in turn can increase public trust in the village government. Bili et al. (2022) added that transparency in governance can strengthen social relations between the government and the community, ultimately contributing to improved community welfare.

According to Bappenas (2021), the success of village fund management depends heavily on the capacity of village officials, community participation, and transparency in budget management. Research by Nurdin, Nugroho, and Kadir (2022) also shows that the combination of adequate village fund allocation and high transparency has a significant impact on village community welfare. Thus, both village fund allocation and transparency play a mutually supportive role in improving village community welfare.

METHOD

This study aims to assess the impact of village fund allocation on the welfare of village communities. This research was conducted in Gampong Pande, Tanah Pasir District, North Aceh Regency, in the 2022 fiscal year. The Regional Inspectorate team had already conducted an audit in 2022, while the 2023-2024 audit had not yet been conducted, and the village head had not yet granted permission to conduct the research.

This study used quantitative methods to determine the relationship or influence of village fund allocation on community welfare. Therefore, the results are expected to provide suggestions for more transparent village fund allocation in Gampong Pande.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Classical Assumption Test

These basic assumptions are crucial to ensuring that the resulting regression coefficient estimates are unbiased. If all these assumptions are met, the estimation results will be more accurate and reliable.

Conversely, if these assumptions are violated, the coefficient estimates can be biased, potentially leading to errors in data interpretation and conclusion drawing.

Normality Test

The normality test aims to determine whether the independent and dependent variables in a regression model are normally distributed. Normality testing can be done using histogram graphs, normal probability plots, and the Kolmogorov-Smirnov (KS) statistical test. The following: Data normality testing is more accurate using a Normal Probability Plot graph than a histogram because this method compares the cumulative distribution of data with a normal distribution.

Figure 1 Normality Probability Plot Graph

Source: Research Results, 2025 (processed data)

Based on Figure 1 above, it can be concluded that the regression model meets the normality assumption because the data is spread around the diagonal line and the data distribution is in the same direction following the diagonal line.

Multicollinearity Test

Multicollinearity test is used to determine whether there is a perfect linear relationship between independent variables, the regression model assumes there is no perfect linear relationship between independent variables. Detection of multicollinearity by looking at the *Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) value* from the results of the regression analysis, if the VIF value is > 5 then there is a high degree of multicollinearity Sumodiningrat, (1999:286). The results of the multicollinearity test can be presented in the following table:

**Table 1
Multicollinearity Test Results**

Variables	Collinearity Statistics		Information
	Tolerance	VIF	
Village Fund Allocation	0.345	2,899	There is no multicollinearity
Transparency	0.369	2,711	There is no multicollinearity

THE EFFECT OF VILLAGE FUND ALLOCATION AND TRANSPARENCY ON THE WELFARE OF THE PANDE GAMPONG COMMUNITY, TANAH PASIR DISTRICT, NORTH ACEH REGENCY

Khairunnisak et al

The results of the multicollinearity test in Table 1 show that each independent variable has a VIF value <5, this shows that there is no perfect relationship between the independent variables, from these results it can be concluded that there are no symptoms of multicollinearity in the regression model.

Heteroscedasticity Test

The heteroscedasticity test aims to test whether there is inequality in the variance of the residuals from one observation to another in the regression model. In conducting heteroscedasticity testing, it can be done through graphical analysis by reading the *Scatterplot graph*, where heteroscedasticity does not occur if the points are spread randomly, do not form a clear pattern, and are spread both above and below the number zero on the Y axis.

Figure 2 Scatterplot Graph

Figure 2 The scatterplot shows that the points are randomly distributed, both above and below zero on the Y-axis, and that the points form a clear pattern. Therefore, the regression model does not experience heteroscedasticity.

Discussion of Results

Regression Analysis

Regression analysis is used to see the influence between the quality of regional apparatus, regulations, accountability on asset management in the North Aceh District Government, as presented in Table 2 below:

**Table 2
Recapitulation of Regression Analysis Results**

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3,438	1,388		2,477	0.015
	Village Fund Allocation	0.267	0.089	0.257	3,005	0.003
	Transparency	0.172	0.083	0.184	2,064	0.042
A. Dependent Variable: Community Welfare						

Source: Processed SPSS data, 2025.

Based on Table 2, the regression equation formed in this regression test is as follows:

$$Y = 3,438 + 0,267X_1 + 0.172X_2 + e$$

The description of the multiple linear regression equation above is as follows:

1. The results of the multiple linear regression equation above obtained a constant value (a) of 3.438, which shows that when the independent variables, namely Village Fund Allocation and Transparency, have a constant value, then the value of the dependent variable, Community Welfare, is 3.433.
2. The regression coefficient of the Village Fund Allocation variable has a positive value of 0.267, indicating a positive relationship, which means that every change in Village Fund Allocation causes Community Welfare to increase by 0.267.
3. The regression coefficient of the Transparency variable has a positive value of 0.172, indicating a positive relationship, which means that every change in Transparency causes Community Welfare to increase by 0.172.

Hypothesis Testing

Partial Test (t-Test)

Partial hypothesis testing, namely determining the variables that have a dominant influence on employee performance, is carried out using the t-test, namely to test the significance of the partial regression coefficient, so that it can be compared which variables have a significant and dominant influence on asset management, which can be explained in Table 3 as follows:

Table 3
Partial Test Results

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3,438	1,388		2,477	0.015
	Village Fund Allocation	0.267	0.089	0.257	3,005	0.003
	Transparency	0.172	0.083	0.184	2,064	0.042
A. Dependent Variable: Community Welfare						

Source: Processed data (2025)

To determine the Ttable value, the tablet statistics attachment is used using a 95% confidence level, (-0.05%) with (df)=(nk) =100-3= 97 so that the Ttable value is 1.66071. Based on the results of the partial significance test in table 4.9, the results are as follows:

1. The test results of Village Fund Allocation (X1) on customer satisfaction obtained a t-value of 3.005 > 1.66071 and a significant value of 0.003 < 0.05. Therefore, it can be concluded that Village Fund Allocation has a partial effect on Community Welfare.
2. The results of the Transparency (X2) test on customer satisfaction obtained a t-value of 2.064 > 1.66071 and a significant value of 0.042 < 0.05. Therefore, it can be concluded that Transparency has a partial effect on Community Welfare.

F Test (Simultan)

Out of reach Test F

ANOVA ^b						
Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	578.94	3	192.98	114,891	.000 ^a
	Residual	161.25	96	1.68		
	Total	740.19	99			
a. Predictors: (Constant), Village Fund Allocation, Transparency						
b. Dependent Variable: Community Welfare						

Source : Results Study (Data diolah 2025)

From Table 4 shows results of the F test Which menghasilkan $F_{hitung} = 114,891 > 3,087 F_{tabel}$ oleh Because That can disimpulkan that variabel Village Fund Allocation and Transparency have an influence in this way significant is concerned with Community Welfare Gampong Pande, Tanah Pasir District, North Aceh Regency.

Coefficient of Determination (R^2)

Based on the results of the multiple linear regression analysis, the correlation value and coefficient of determination can also be determined, where the correlation value reflects the strength of the relationship between the independent variables of Village Fund Allocation and Transparency. on the dependent variable (Community Welfare). The coefficient of determination value can be seen in Table 5 as follows:

Table 45
Results of the Determination Coefficient Test

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Standard Error of the Estimate
1	.840 ^a	.705	.696	2,133
a. Predictors: (Constant), Village Fund Allocation, Transparency				
b. Dependent Variable: Community Welfare				

Source: Processed data (2025)

Model Summary analysis in Table 5, it can be seen that the correlation coefficient (R) value of 0.840 indicates a strong relationship, amounting to 84%, between the independent variables (Village Fund Allocation) and Village Fund Allocation. And Transparency) on the dependent variable of Community Welfare. This means that these independent variables have a close relationship with Community Welfare. The remaining 16% is influenced by other factors outside this study. Furthermore, the coefficient of determination (*R Square*) value of 0.705 indicates that 70.5% of the variation in Community Welfare can be explained by variations in Village Fund Allocation. And Transparency . The remaining 29.5% is influenced by factors outside the research model. The Adjusted R Square value

of 0.696 indicates that after accounting for the number of independent variables and sample size, the regression model is still able to explain 69.6% of the variation in Community Welfare. The remaining 30.4% is influenced by factors outside the model.

Discussion

The Impact of Village Fund Allocation on Community Welfare

The results of the partial hypothesis test show that the allocation of village funds (X) has a positive and significant effect on community welfare (Y) which means H1 is accepted with the results of the t-test of 3.005. The results of this study are in line with previous research conducted by Fathony, Aditya Achmad (2019) which shows that the allocation of village funds has a positive and significant effect on community empowerment where this community empowerment aims to provide welfare to village communities. The results of this study are also in line with research conducted by Hariyani, Desi (2018) and who in their research said that the variable of village fund allocation has a significant effect on the welfare of village communities. This proves that the allocation of village funds has an effect on the welfare of village communities which is also supported by the theory of Fahrudin (2012), community welfare has the goal of achieving a prosperous life in the sense of achieving basic living standards and to achieve good adjustment, especially with the community in their environment, for example by exploring sources to improve and develop a satisfactory standard of living. Achieving prosperity is not easy, so in running its government, Gampong Pande, Tanah Pasir District, North Aceh Regency, requires good programs to improve the welfare of the village community. One of these programs is the Village Allocation Fund (ADD). This program is a program designed by the Indonesian government to accelerate poverty alleviation in an integrated and sustainable manner, focusing on achieving the welfare and independence of the rural poor.

Based on the results of the statistical tests and the discussion presented, it can be concluded that the hypothesis in this study is accepted with a t-count of $3.005 > 1.66071$ and a significance value of $0.003 < 0.05$. Therefore, it can be concluded that Village Fund Allocation has a partial effect on Community Welfare.

The Impact of Transparency on Public Welfare

The results of the study indicate that transparency has a significant effect on community welfare in Gampong Pande, Tanah Pasir District, North Aceh Regency. This finding is indicated by the t-value of 2.064 which is greater than the t-table of 1.98498, and a significance value of 0.042 which is smaller than 0.05. Thus, the hypothesis stating that transparency has a positive and significant effect on community welfare is accepted (H2). Transparency is able to create mutual trust between the village government and the community through the provision of information and ensuring ease in obtaining accurate and adequate information. All communities have the opportunity to obtain access to information related to the transparency of village fund management, so that the more open the government is to the management of village funds, the more it increases community trust in the government. *Stewardship Theory* in the development of this hypothesis assumes that the village government is essentially trustworthy, responsible, and has integrity towards the Talang Baru village community.

The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Mandy Tania Sari and Titik Mildawati (2020) which stated that transparency in the management of village fund allocations has a significant impact on community welfare.

The Influence of Village Fund Allocation and Transparency on Community Welfare

Results of the F test Which $m e n g a s i l k a n F_{h i t u n g} = 114,891 > 3,087 F_{t a b e l o l e h}$ Because That can disimpulkan that variabel Village Fund Allocation and Transparency have an influence in this way signifikan is concerned with Community Welfare Pande Village, Tanah Pasir District, North Aceh Regency. Village fund allocation is a fiscal instrument to encourage development and improve the welfare of village communities. Village funds contribute to infrastructure development, improve basic services, and strengthen the local economy, thus positively impacting the community's quality of life. However, their effectiveness depends heavily on good governance, particularly transparency and accountability. Transparency in village fund management is positively correlated with community welfare because it increases trust, participation, and accountability. The more transparent budget information is, the more effective village programs are in improving welfare, particularly through community involvement in planning and evaluation. Furthermore, a study by Nurdin, Nugroho, and Kadir (2022) shows that the combination of the size of village fund allocation and the level of transparency are key factors in determining the success of village development. They conducted a regression analysis of 100 villages in South Sulawesi and found that villages with high levels of transparency and targeted fund use tended to have better welfare indices. The welfare indicators used in this study included household income, access to health services, education, and community satisfaction with public services. This study confirms that the influence of village funds on welfare is not linear, but is moderated by governance variables.

In the context of policy implementation, research from Bappenas (2021) found that the success of village funds depends on the capacity of village officials, community participation in planning, and transparency in financial management. Community involvement and information transparency encourage targeted budget allocation, efficient use of funds, and equitable distribution of development outcomes. Meanwhile, a longitudinal analysis by Syahputra and Sari (2020) found that the increase in village fund allocations from 2015–2019 did not always have a significant impact on welfare due to budget misuse, weak oversight, and a lack of transparency. Without good governance, the amount of funds does not guarantee improved welfare, making village management reform crucial. A study by Wahyuni and Nasution (2023) specifically examined the relationship between village budget transparency and perceptions of community welfare in West Java. Their results showed that communities who felt involved and had access to village financial information demonstrated higher levels of satisfaction with development outcomes. This active participation was also positively correlated with an increase in the local happiness index and strengthened social capital at the community level. They concluded that transparency not only impacts the economic aspect, but also the psychosocial aspect of village communities.

Additionally, a report from the Ministry of Villages, Development of Disadvantaged Regions, and Transmigration (Kemendes PDTT, 2023) shows that the implementation of the Village Financial System (Siskeudes) has increased the transparency and efficiency of village fund management in many regions. Villages that have adopted this system have shown improvements in the timeliness of financial reports, public information transparency, and a decrease in village fund corruption cases. This data demonstrates that an information technology approach can be a strategic solution for improving village fund governance, which in turn positively impacts community welfare.

THE EFFECT OF VILLAGE FUND ALLOCATION AND TRANSPARENCY ON THE WELFARE OF THE PANDE GAMPONG COMMUNITY, TANAH PASIR DISTRICT, NORTH ACEH REGENCY

Khairunnisak et al

CONCLUSION

The results of the study indicate that Village Fund Allocation and Transparency both significantly influence the welfare of the Pande Village community. Partially, Village Fund Allocation ($t_{count} = 3.005$; $p = 0.003$) and Transparency ($t_{count} = 2.064$; $p = 0.042$) have a positive effect on community welfare. Simultaneously, these two variables also have a significant effect together on community welfare ($F_{count} = 114.891 > F_{table} = 3.087$). The Pande Village Government is advised to prioritize Village Fund Allocation on programs that directly improve community welfare, such as infrastructure, economic empowerment, education, and health, with a participatory budget preparation. In addition, transparency in fund management must be improved through open information that is easily accessible to residents. Integrating the use of funds appropriately with the principle of transparency is consistently important to maximize the impact of inclusive, participatory, and sustainable village development.

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